

SUPPLEMENT 1. Color card of the colors referred to in this study. The color names were designated following the color nomenclature code for description works of specimens in Kun L. Yang's private herbarium (HTBM) (Yang 2023).

No.	Sample	Color Name		Color Code	Note
		Chinese	English		
\		瓷白色	ceramic white	#FEFEFA	Previously designated
\		淡褐色	light brown	#B39966	Previously designated
\		土橙色	earthy orange	#CF8A45	Previously designated
\		中灰色	medium gray	#E0DEDD	Previously designated
\		海狸褐色	beaver brown	#9D7B69	Previously designated
\		羊毛白色	merino white	#F9F5EC	Previously designated
\		沙橙色	sandy orange	#E6CF73	Previously designated
\		枇杷橙色	loquat orange	#F3D390	Previously designated
57		肉褐色	meat brown	#D7B19D	Designated in this study
58		檀香褐色	sandal brown	#BA8B70	Designated in this study
59		深胡椒红色	dark pepper red	#764840	Designated in this study
60		锈橙色	rust orange	#D79A65	Designated in this study
61		污蓝色	dirty blue	#A4BAC0	Designated in this study
62		海军蓝色	cadet blue	#A9B5C3	Designated in this study
63		暗草黄色	dull thatch yellow	#D3D3B7	Designated in this study
64		暗粉霜红色	dull blush red	#CDA19C	Designated in this study
65		茄子粉色	eggplant pink	#714957	Designated in this study
66		黑加仑紫红色	blackcurrant purple	#422F45	Designated in this study
67		砖橙色	brick orange	#ECE2B4	Designated in this study
68		淡米褐色	pale beige brown	#E0CDA5	Designated in this study
69		淡肉褐色	pale meat brown	#E4C8BB	Designated in this study
70		草黄色	thatch yellow	#F1ECC5	Designated in this study
71		亮柚木褐色	bright teak brown	#AF9C6D	Designated in this study
72		茶橙色	tea orange	#EFDFA0	Designated in this study
73		污黄铜褐色	dirty brass brown	#B47F5A	Designated in this study
74		油橙色	butter orange	#F2DF8F	Designated in this study
75		暗污橙色	dull dirty orange	#EBD087	Designated in this study
76		亮土橙色	bright earthy orange	#E3B163	Designated in this study
77		石南褐色	heathered brown	#B7AB8F	Designated in this study
78		暗银灰色	dull silver gray	#A7A6A5	Designated in this study
79		礁石褐色	reef brown	#CCC2A6	Designated in this study
80		珍珠木褐色	lacewood brown	#D5B7A1	Designated in this study
81		南瓜橙色	pumpkin orange	#CEB640	Designated in this study
82		豆蔻黄色	cardamon yellow	#E0E091	Designated in this study
83		螺壳白色	conch white	#EFEFF7	Designated in this study
84		紫藤紫色	wisteria violet	#C5BBDC	Designated in this study
85		洋桔梗紫色	lisianthus violet	#846994	Designated in this study
86		暗丝绸褐色	dull silk brown	#C3B3A6	Designated in this study
87		金橙色	golden orange	#E4CB4E	Designated in this study
88		沙漠橙色	desert orange	#E8D7B0	Designated in this study
89		猪白色	pig white	#FDF7F2	Designated in this study
90		鸡肉橙色	chicken orange	#F8DCC9	Designated in this study
91		风滚草橙色	tumbleweed orange	#E8B28F	Designated in this study
92		大麦褐色	barley brown	#E6D1B5	Designated in this study
93		陈皮橙色	tangerine-peel orange	#CD6425	Designated in this study
94		亚麻褐色	linen brown	#E6DECB	Designated in this study
95		焦糖橙色	caramel orange	#DB8E37	Designated in this study
96		乳黄色	milky yellow	#FFF07A	Designated in this study
97		沙滩黄色	beach yellow	#F9F3C9	Designated in this study
98		滨螺蓝色	periwinkle blue	#CDCFE5	Designated in this study
99		紫檀红色	rosewood red	#78545C	Designated in this study
100		淡滨螺蓝色	pale periwinkle blue	#C9D4E6	Designated in this study
101		暗鸽蓝色	dull pigeon blue	#A9B5C3	Designated in this study
102		淡骨褐色	pale bone brown	#E7D5C7	Designated in this study
103		泥潭褐色	mire brown	#B89F89	Designated in this study
104		枯叶绿色	withered green	#D5DCB7	Designated in this study
105		脏绿色	muck green	#92A890	Designated in this study
106		污草红色	dirty thatch red	#BFA5A5	Designated in this study
107		暗草红色	dull thatch red	#B29B9C	Designated in this study
108		污乳褐色	dirty milky brown	#B7A48D	Designated in this study
109		锆白色	zircon white	#F3F5FD	Designated in this study
110		石膏白色	alabaster white	#F9F9F9	Designated in this study
111		布褐色	cotton brown	#D2CAAD	Designated in this study
112		狮橙色	lion orange	#EFD871	Designated in this study
113		樱桃木褐色	cherrywood brown	#DAB697	Designated in this study
114		月黄色	moon yellow	#FAF9AA	Designated in this study
115		魔黄色	mana yellow	#F7F57E	Designated in this study
116		昏橙色	dusk orange	#CEAD64	Designated in this study
117		阴天蓝色	overcast blue	#D6DBE7	Designated in this study
118		污紫藤紫色	dirty wisteria violet	#C5BCCC	Designated in this study
119		牛排紫红色	steak purple	#877280	Designated in this study
120		污天蓝色	dirty sky blue	#BED5DB	Designated in this study
121		沙绿色	sand green	#B2C4B5	Designated in this study
122		水墨绿色	ink green	#9DB1A7	Designated in this study
123		淡石板蓝色	pale slate blue	#688D99	Designated in this study
124		大麦橙色	barley orange	#E4C8A4	Designated in this study
125		淡褐色	pale brown	#E3DECC	Designated in this study
126		暗丝绸红色	dull silk red	#BBA8A2	Designated in this study
127		鸭血红色	duck blood red	#564843	Designated in this study
128		泥褐色	muddy brown	#BD936D	Designated in this study
129		咖啡豆褐色	coffee-bean brown	#483625	Designated in this study
130		湿沙黄色	wet sand yellow	#CCC796	Designated in this study
131		淡污橙色	pale dirty orange	#FAF4E3	Designated in this study
132		暗橙色	dull orange	#E3C4A3	Designated in this study
133		布丁橙色	pudding orange	#FFE8A3	Designated in this study
134		淡乳橙色	pale milky orange	#FFEDA2	Designated in this study
135		金鸡菊橙色	goldenrod orange	#F9D873	Designated in this study
136		亮焦糖褐色	bright caramel orange	#EB9300	Designated in this study
137		暗金橙色	dull golden orange	#D8B77B	Designated in this study